

D8.3 <Promo material design>

WP8

Lead Partner: FENIX

Partner Contributors: All

Dissemination Level: PU

Deliverable due date: M7 Actual submission date: M7

Deliverable Version: V1

Project Acronym	EnDurCrete
Project Title	New Environmental friendly and Durable conCrete, integrating industrial by-products and hybrid systems, for civil, industrial and offshore applications
Grant Agreement n°	760639
Funding Scheme	Research Innovation Action
Call	H2020-NMBP-2017
Topic	NMBP-06-2017 Improved material durability in buildings and infrastructures, including offshore
Starting Date	1 st January 2018
Duration	42 Months

Executive Summary

The Deliverable D8.3 is a public document of the EnDurCrete project, delivered in the context of WP8 Training, dissemination and exploitation, Task 8.1 Dissemination, Communication and Networking. The objective of WP8 is to secure the successful dissemination of the EnDurCrete project through the implementation and deployment of an awareness and dissemination plan.

The purpose of this document is to describe the activities that were carried on during the first seven months of the EnDurCrete project in order to prepare and support the project dissemination material, in particular including project logo and logo manual, project templates, brochure, poster and project presentation in English. The document describes in detail different types of dissemination materials produced, process and players that have contributed to their preparation.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

[WP] – Work Package

[D] – Deliverable

[T] – Task

[M] – Month

[PU] - Public

1 Introduction

The objective of WP8 is to secure the successful dissemination through the implementation and deployment of an awareness and dissemination plan to identify and organize the activities to be performed in order to promote the commercial exploitation of the project's results and the widest dissemination of knowledge from the project.

A relevant part of the dissemination activities foreseen in the project depends on the production of high quality dissemination material able to communicate project results and activities to the target audience. For this purpose, a group of initial dissemination tools were developed to support communication and dissemination, in particular:

- Project logo and logo manual
- Project templates
- PowerPoint project presentation
- Project brochure
- Project roll-up poster

This document describes the delivered material that has been produced during the first seven months of the EnDurCrete project.

2 Project visual identity

Objectives of the project identity are:

- To develop a design structure that would accommodate standard project identity elements, a variable visual identity in various uses, and be able to convey thematic information when needed.
- To allow an immediate recognition of the EnDurCrete project thanks to standardized communication templates meant for external audiences.
- To develop specific guidelines and structures related to such template such as a definite set of colors and/or typography. These guidelines should be applied to templates that are easy to adapt, to understand and to use by the project partners.

2.1 Project logo

Initial task for the dissemination material design is logo development. The logo has been created in vector resolution at the beginning of the project in order to define a project identity, and clearly identify any kind of internal or public document (deliverables, reports, internal communications, publications, etc.).

EnDurCrete logo consists of grey cube representing concrete product, which is the core of the project. The green side of the cube illustrates the fact that the concrete developed under the EnDurCrete project takes into consideration environmental aspects and is expected to have improved LCA compared to traditional concrete. The second component of the logo consists of the name of the project in corresponding colours.

Figure 2.1 EnDurCrete logo

The corporate image of EnDurCrete rests upon the use of three colors: green, light grey and dark grey. The EnDurCrete logo font used is Proxima Nova Bold.

Figure 2.2 Palette of logo colors

It is important to follow and respect the project visual identity in order to maximize the impact on the audience. For this reason, a Logo manual has been prepared, outlining the visual identity guidelines (master brand logo, color palette, logo usage, logo clear zone, relation to other logos, typography, file formats, applications and errors to avoid). The EnDurCrete logo manual is available on the project website in section “Documents – Promo material - Logo”.

Figure 2.3 Logo manual

The Project logo can be used in the following cases:

- in all documents developed under the framework of the EnDurCrete project; in documents to be submitted to the EC (e.g. deliverables);
- in project presentations and in dissemination material to be used for communication and dissemination activities carried out by each project participant under the framework of the project;
- on the EnDurCrete website, and on websites of the project participants with a link to the project website.

2.2 Project templates

Various formats of templates have been prepared (Word and PowerPoint) and developed in order to provide partners with “ready-to-be-used” documents that will comply with the corporate image. These templates must be used by the partners whenever possible when the EnDurCrete project is presented, for instance for press releases or presentations related to the project during events. The font which has been selected, to be used for Word documents and PowerPoint presentation is Calibri.

Figure 2.4 Template of PowerPoint presentation

DX.X <Title>
WPs
Lead Partner: XXX
 Partner Contributor: XXX, XXX, XXX

Dissemination Level: XXX
 Deliverable due date: MM Actual submission date: MM
 Deliverable Version: VX

Project Acronym	EU4C/Cre
Project Title	New Environmental Ready and Durable concrete, integrating industrial, bio-products and hybrid systems for civil, industrial and offshore applications
Grant Agreement n°	740493
Funding Scheme	Research Innovation Action
Call	H2020-NMP-2017
Topic	NMP-06-2017 Integrated material durability in buildings and infrastructures, including offshore
Starting Date	17 January 2018
Duration	42 Months

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Executive Summary
 Please write a concise summary, including clear goal of this document, most important results, clear conclusions (link with goals).

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Abbreviations and Acronyms
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 [00]-xxxxxxxx

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1 Introduction
 Probably the best to start at a new page.

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2 Your first chapter name
 Probably the best to start at a new page.

Figure 2.1 - YOUR EXAMPLE

Column 1	Column 2	Column 3	Column 4	Column 5

2.1 Your first subchapter name
 Please insert text.

2.1.1 Your first subchapter name
 Please insert text.

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Figure 2.5 Template of Word document

3 Dissemination material

For the first seven months of the project initial dissemination material has been developed to support communication and dissemination activities of the EnDurCrete project as part of the task T8.1 Dissemination, Communication and Networking. The dissemination material was created preferably in English and will be updated every twelve months after the project meetings following the project progression, considering the future translation to partners' mother languages. All dissemination material is available on the EnDurCrete project website (www.endurcrete.eu).

3.1 PowerPoint presentation

The project presentation in PowerPoint has been designed for the EnDurCrete project by the end of month 7 by FENIX. The project presentation includes general information of the project, overall concept, objectives, overall approach, expected impact and information about demonstration. Furthermore, contact information, a website link, partners and the statement of financial support to indicate that the foreground was generated with the assistance of financial support from the European Union and disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility.

Figure 3.1 PowerPoint project presentation

3.2 Project brochure

FENIX, who is responsible for any dissemination update related to any progress of the project, has designed and prepared the brochure (unfolded format A4, 210x297mm) for the EnDurCrete project by the end of month 5 with a more general overview about the project.

The leaflet is describing the overall concept of the project, project objectives, overall approach, expected impact and demonstration information. Furthermore, it gives a website and social media links, QR code, contact information, partners' logos and finally the statement of financial support to indicate that the foreground was generated with the assistance of financial support from the European Union and disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility.

Following the project evolution, also a scientific brochure is planned to be developed for the specific target audience.

Figure 3.2 Project brochure

3.3 Project roll-up poster

The one page roll-up poster (format 85x200cm) has been designed for the EnDurCrete project by the end of month 5 following the leaflet design by FENIX. The roll-up poster includes acronym and main goal of the project, the website and social media links, partners' logos and the statement of financial support to indicate that the foreground was generated with the assistance of financial support from the European Union and disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility.

Figure 3.3 Project roll-up poster

4 Future work

It is currently foreseen that the following will be carried out in due course:

- ✓ Scientific brochure creation
- ✓ Dissemination material translation to partners' language
- ✓ Continuous update of dissemination material based on the project progress
- ✓ Newsletter design
- ✓ Project promo video creation

The progress and results of these actions will be described in deliverables D8.7 Progress report on dissemination and networking activities and awareness campaign and D8.11 Final report on dissemination and networking activities and awareness campaign.

5 Conclusion

All dissemination material – brochure, poster and project presentation – has been designed and created with the intention of updating them every twelve months following the project progress, and can be found on the project website public section – documents. A scientific leaflet is planned to be created besides the commercial one for the specific target audience. Dissemination material has been created preferably in English language, considering future translation in the partners' mother language.